

MOLDING PROCESS OPTIMIZATION OF A FAST CURING EPOXY RESIN PREPREG WITH LONG TIME STORAGE AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

Fast curing epoxy resin prepreg are required if continuous carbon fiber reinforced plastic are to be economically viable material choices in industrial area such as automotive parts and sporting goods in recent years. We have developed ACTECH[®]1201 fast curing epoxy resin system to match the emergence of demand in rapid curing composites. This type of resin and prepreg could cure in less than five minutes under temperatures ranging from 130 to 150 Celsius with long time storage ($\geq 60d$) at room temperature, excellent mechanical properties and high Tg up to 146°C. Prepreg compression moulding manufacturing process suitable for automated production and fast manufacturing were investigated using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Dynamic thermal Mechanical Analysis (DMA), Gel time test and mechanical properties characterization. Key process parameters such as curing temperature, curing time and pressing temperature and pressure were obtained and a suitable fast curing composites molding process was established. We also tested the mechanics performance and surface topography of the fast curing composite cured with the obtained process. The composite's properties match the properties of Aeronautical grade medium temperature cure epoxy resin matrix composites. A car bonnet was fast manufactured use ACTECH[®]1201 fast curing carbon fiber fabric prepreg which completely satisfied the needs of automobile industry for fast pace, high efficiency, and large scale production.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials are one of the critical elements in advancing the development of high end Aerospace and Aeronautic equipment, their usage in equipment signifies the equipment's advancement. Industries' demands for industrially applicable advanced composites become increasingly higher recently, however the long curing time and slow manufacturing rate of conventional composites is becoming the bottleneck for industrial applications of composites in automobile, railway transportation and other industries[1-3]. The price of carbon fibers step lower gradually as well as the emergence of rapid curing composites solve the problem of manufacture costs and efficiency effectively provide great opportunities for the application and rapid continuous preparation of composite. The present study involves a new type epoxy system designed for use with short cycle time composites molding processes and key process parameters optimization satisfied the needs of automobile industry[4-6].

2 EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

2.1 Materials and Methods

The fast curing resin system named ACTECH®1201 studied in this project was created by us. It is a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy system with high viscosity and high toughness suitable for prepreg manufacture.

Carbon fiber and fabric as well as other minor handicraft materials used for mechanical properties test by autoclave process and key process parameters optimization in composites molding process are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Composites mechanical test projects and standards

Name	Grade	Materials	Supplier
Carbon Fiber	T700S	—	Toray
Carbon Fiber Twill Fabric	W3021	TR30S-3K(Mitsubishi)	Changzhou TiWin composite Co.LTD
Bagging Film	WN1500	Nylon	Airtech
Breather Fabric	ULtraweave®1332	Nylon	Airtech
Non-perforated Release Film	A4000	FEP	Airtech
Release Film	Release Ease 234TFP	Fiberglass	Airtech
Peel Ply	Release Ply B	Nylon	Airtech
Release Agent	PMR	—	Airtech
Sealant Tape	GS-213-2	—	Airtech

Lay-up and assemble of prepreps for mechanical properties test in autoclave process as shown in Figure 1. The degree of cure, heat of reaction and the residual heat of reaction for the fast cured resin were measured by a Mettler DSC equipment using about 5 mg of resin in aluminium pans with heating rate 10 °C/min from room temperature to 200 °C. Dynamic thermal Mechanical Analysis (DMA) were conducted to determine the glass transition temperature T_g at a heating rate of 5 °C/min from room temperature to 200 °C using a TA Q1000. All the measurements were performed using a nitrogen sample purge flow to reduce oxidation of the resin. A Anton Paar Physica MCR101 plate-plate rheometer was used to measure the change in viscosity with a strain of 1 % and an angular frequency of 10 s⁻¹. Composites mechanical test projects and standards are given in Table 2.

Fig1. Lay-up and assemble of prepregs for mechanical properties test

Table 2 Composites mechanical test projects and standards

Mechanical properties	Unite	Test standard
0° Tensile strength	MPa	ASTM D 3039
90° Tensile strength	MPa	ASTM D 3039
0° Compressive strength	MPa	ASTM D 6641
0° Flexural strength	MPa	ASTM D 790
Short-beam strength	MPa	ASTM D 2344
CAI	MPa	ASTM D 7137

2.2 Physical and Chemical Property of Resin

The heat flow was measured under rising conditions from RT(Room Temperature) to 200 °C in a 10°C interval for the fast curing epoxy as shown in Figure 2. The resin system under analysis reacts quickly as temperature is elevated up to about 130°C and the whole reaction heat is 296.7J/g, therefore the suitable curing temperature is 130°C ~150°C. The heat flow peaks at the beginning of the reaction at a very low degree of cure for all measurements which indicates that a high amount of heat will be released in the beginning of the cure reaction and the resin system have excellent room and low temperature stability. The measured maximum heat flow shows equal with standard curing epoxies which alleviate the explosion problems caused by the huge heat of reaction.

Rheological properties of resin measured by plate-plate rheometer exhibit consistency with DSC test results as shown in Figure 3. The viscosity of resin increase rapidly in 120°C ~130 °C while the reaction start at the same temperature concluded from DSC results. The suitable process parameters for prepreg manufacture and curing process pressure point are 50°C~80 °C and 90°C~110 °C which can also obtained from viscosity-temperature curve in Figure 3. All the results indicate that the suitable curing temperature of the fast curing epoxy resin should be at 120°C ~150°C.

Fig 2. DSC experiment of fast curing epoxy resin

Fig 3. Rheological properties of fast curing epoxy resin

Rheological properties of resin were then measured under isothermal conditions at 80°C, 100°C, 130°C and 150°C as shown in Figure 4. The viscosity of resin increase rapidly in minutes at 130°C and 150 °C condition while increase slowly at 80°C and 100°C conditions also prove that the ACTECH®1201 can quickly react under 130°C and 150 °C conditions. Then the gel times of resin were tested under 130°C and 150 °C conditions which can also provide evidence for previous conclusions as shown in Figure 5. Gel times of fast curing resin were 4.8min at 130°C condition and 2.0min at 150°C condition in multiple batches average.

Fig 4. Rheological properties of resin under different temperature conditions

Fig 5. Gel time of fast curing epoxy resin

2.3 Physical and Chemical Property of Prepreg

A type of carbon fiber twill fabric reinforced fast curing epoxy resin prepreg and a type of carbon fiber prepreg named ACTECH®1201/W3021 and ACTECH®1201/T700 were manufactured and specification of prepreg's physical properties, such as areal density of prepreg, areal density of carbon fiber fabric as well as the resin content et al. were tested and listed in Table 3. According to the basic physical properties of the prepreg, its showing the stability and uniform consistency production process of prepreg.

Table 3 Physical properties of ACTECH®1201/W3021

Physical properties	Unite	Result	
		ACTECH®1201/ W3021	ACTECH®1201/ T700S
Areal density of prepreg	g/m ²	326	196
Areal density of carbon fiber fabric	g/m ²	198	132
Resin content	%	39.2	32.7
Volatiles content	%	0.16	0.09

We established a preliminary basic program for curing process that heating rate is 1-3°C/min from RT to 130°C and curing time at 130°C degrees is 15min in autoclave process according to the DSC test results, rheological properties and gel time. Based on this process, a group of test samples of fast curing composites were manufactured and tested using ASTM standards in order to obtain the composites mechanical properties which are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Composites mechanical test projects and results

Mechanical properties	Unite	Test condition	Result
0° Tensile strength	MPa	-55°C dry	2646
		RT dry	2683
		80°C dry	2587
		80°C wet	1953
90° Tensile strength	MPa	-55°C dry	48.3
		RT dry	46.4
		80°C dry	50.3
0° Compressive strength	MPa	-55°C dry	1237
		RT dry	1177
		80°C dry	928
		80°C wet	453
0° Flexural strength	MPa	RT dry	1747
Short-beam strength	MPa	-55°C dry	106
		RT dry	75
		80°C dry	48.6
		80°C wet	24.8
CAI	MPa	RT dry	218

The glass transition temperature(T_g) of composite was also tested using DMA method at the same time as shown in Figure 6 which indicate the prepreg can be cured at 130°C under 15 min and perform excellent thermostability. T_g of composites is as high as 146°C equal with common medium temperature curing prepreps used in aeronautics field.

Fig 6. The glass transition temperature of the composites

The mechanical properties of fast curing composite materials were tested in four states, -55°C dry, RT dry, 80°C dry and 80°C wet with sock in water for 14d. The detail material properties of ACTECH®1201/T700S composite is listed in Table 4 which shows the composite has comprehensive excellent mechanical properties with 130 °C/15min curing process in autoclave process and the properties of the fast curing composite corresponded to commonly-used epoxy in the aerospace industry in autoclave process. The composite also have excellent high temperature resistance and can keeps excellent mechanical properties at low temperature at the same time while it can keep about 80% strength of RT performance equal with commonly-used epoxy used in aeronautics field. This material also has excellent toughness with the compression after impact strength as high as 218 MPa. All this make clear that the material can obtain excellent mechanical properties and temperature resistance in fast curing process and it can be used in a variety of capacity and non-bearing structures.

The storage time at outdoor room temperature of fast curing prepreg were also tested by DSC and Gel time test listed in table 5 which indicated the storage time at outdoor room temperature of this fast curing prepreg can reach as long as 60 days at least.

Table 5 Fast storage of prepregs for outdoor storage

Number	Outdoor storage/days	DSC results		Gel time/ min	
		Onset temperature/°C	reaction heat/ (J/g)	130°C	150°C
1#	0	130.4	296	4:48	2:01
2#	15	130.6	289	4:36	1:58
3#	30	131.2	291	4:56	2:12
4#	45	126.5	273	4:03	1:57
5#	60	125.6	268	3:51	1:46

2.4 Rapid Molding Process Optimization

The rapid molding process of fast curing composite were studied in order to optimize the demand of short-time manufacture in industrial area such as automotive parts and sporting goods. We designed some parameters of rapid molding process which are listed in Table 6 based on the results of DSC, DMA and experimental of process in 130 °C/15min curing process. Experiments were conducted follow Table 6 in order to meet the rapid solidification requirement and limit the whole process time within 1 hour. The short-beam strength, DMA and surface topographies were also tested at the same time which are listed in Table 6. We have summarized the pressing temperature 110°C, pressure 2MPa, curing temperature 130°C and curing time 15min process as the most suitable parameters of rapid molding process when all the results are considered which can obtain excellent surface quality, excellent mechanical

properties and heat stability. A large auto part was then manufactured follow this selected process.

Table 6 Rapid curing molding process parameters

Onset temperature	Pressing temperature and pressure	Curing time and temperature	Short-beam strength/MPa	Tg tested by DMA/°C	surface quality
150°C	150°C/2MPa	150°C/5min	75.4	146.8	+
130°C	130°C/2MPa	130°C/5min	66.9	137.8	++
130°C	130°C/2MPa	130°C/10min	67.1	136.0	++
130°C	130°C/2MPa	130°C/15min	77.1	147.8	++
130°C	130°C/2MPa	130°C/30min	78.3	144.6	++
130°C	130°C/2MPa	130°C/60min	73.2	146.0	++
110°C	110°C/2MPa	130°C/15min	80.0	144.7	++++
110°C	110°C/2MPa	130°C/30min	77.2	142.8	++++
80°C	80°C/2MPa	130°C/15min	76.9	146.0	+++
80°C	110°C/2MPa	130°C/15min	75.1	146.6	+++

2.5 Manufacture of automotive bonnet in rapid molding process

We manufactured a automotive bonnet as shown in figure 7 according to the selected rapid molding process. This part use ACTECH®1201/W3021 carbon fiber twill fabric reinforced prepreg and the thickness of this bonnet is 1.5mm as well as the width is 1000mm, the length is 1500mm. In the selected rapid molding process, the temperature of bonnet mold remained at $110 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$, the well down lay-up prepreps were then putted in the mold and pressure about 1.5 to 3MPa was conducted as soon as possible. The temperature raised up to 130°C as soon as possible and the curing time set at 130°C for 15 min. The mold opened directly at 130°C as well as the bonnet was taken out. It can be seen that the bonnet manufactured by this rapid molding process have excellent surface quality and shape coherence with complete cured. It can also indicated that this process is suitable for mass production of auto parts.

Fig 7. A automotive bonnet made from fast curing prepreps

9 CONCLUSIONS

The fast curing epoxy resin prepreg could cure in less than five minutes under temperatures ranging from 130 to 150 Celsius with long time storage ($\geq 60\text{d}$) at room temperature obtained from DSC、DMA and Gel time tests and experiments results. The composite's material properties match the properties of Aeronautical grade medium temperature cure epoxy resin matrix composites. Key process parameters such as curing temperature, curing time and pressing temperature and pressure which are 130°C , 15min, 110°C and 1.5-3MPa were obtained as well. The composite cured follow this optimized process have excellent surface quality, excellent mechanical properties and heat stability. A car bonnet was fast manufactured using ACTECH®1201/W3021 carbon fiber twill fabric reinforced prepreg

the optimized rapid molding process indicated that the developed fast curing prepregs are suitable for automated production and fast manufacturing like automatic tape placement and fiber tow placement, and completely satisfies the needs of industries like automobile for fast pace, high efficiency, and large scale production.

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